

Social

IMPACT OF CAREER GUIDANCE AND COUNSELING ON STUDENT'S CAREER DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Face to face career guidance and counseling is effective and important aspect of life. It can make or break career. Career counseling represents an important variable to better understand career intervention underlying mechanisms. The trend of career guidance in India is not satisfactory. Present study is focused on finding of impacts of career guidance and counseling on students regarding career development.

Keywords: Guidance; Counseling; Career Guidance.

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1. Introduction

Career guidance seeks to empower clients to be proactive and believe in their ability to make things happen, boosts confidence in job seeking. Counseling is fundamental of future planning. It encourages a positive reconstruction of the meaning of past experience, to be optimistic, to set constructive external goals and focus on future possibilities.

The construction of social identity is a core activity of counseling because work and learning activities define identity. It promotes good quality work; it seems likely and tends to promote well-being. Counseling promotes participation in work and learning. This means clients may gain opportunities to belong to a social group, avoid loneliness. This enable them to build social ties that may support them in facing future challenges.

Career counseling and guidance affect career decision making process based on theories of traditional counseling. Career is based on student's education, goals, values, interests, vision and skills. Sometime a student is not sure about what strength he has. He does not know what career pathway and his aptitude might support. There are also other factors that might impact their career choices.

Effective career counseling give students a deeper insight into question they have, to help them better plan their future and to actually use their attributes well. It supports people to face career related challenges. Through their expertise in career development and labor market, career counselors can put a person's qualifications, experience, strengths and weakness in a broad perspective considering their desired salary, personal hobbies, interest, location, job market and educational possibilities. Career counselors support people in gaining a better understanding of what really matters for them personally, how they can plan their careers autonomously, help making tough decisions. They are capable of supporting students in finding suitable placements, jobs.

2. Objective of the Study

- To find impacts of career guidance and counseling on student's career development.
- To find satisfaction of guided working persons regarding their profession and comparison with unguided professionals.

3. Hypothesis

- There is a significant effect of career guidance and counseling on student's career development.
- There is a significant effect of career guidance and counseling on professionals working persons regarding job satisfaction.

4. Methodology

For present study a sample of 240 professionals were selected randomly and classified according to their profession. Sample was consists of Engineers, Doctors, Chartered Accountants, Managers, Architects, Software Engineers, Interior Decorators, Dress Designers, Teachers and Lawyers. Each professional group was comprised of 15 male and 15 female. All selected persons were interviewed and tested for effects of career counseling and job satisfaction with the help of a self-prepared questionnaire. Collected data was tabulated, converted into percentage and comparatively analyzed.

5. Finding and Analysis

Table 1: Status of Professionals Received Career Counseling

Profession	No. of Professionals Guided By Career Counselors (%)	No. of Professionals not Guided By Career Counselors (%)
Engineer	17	83
Doctor	23	77
Chartered Accountant	22	78
Managers	14	86
Software Engineer	23	77
Architect	27	73
Interior Decorator	24	76

Dress Designer	21	79
Teacher	13	87
Lawyer	16	84

Chart 1: Status of Professionals Received Career Counseling

Table 2: Status of Satisfaction among Professionals Regarding Their Profession

Profession	Profession Satisfaction Status	
	No. of Professionals Guided By Career Counselors (%)	No. of Professionals not Guided By Career Counselors (%)
Engineer	86	62
Doctor	91	73
Chartered Accountant	97	94
Managers	88	81
Software Engineer	89	78
Architect	84	71
Interior Decorator	86	78
Dress Designer	87	73
Teacher	77	61
Lawyer	71	63

Chart 2: Status of Satisfaction among Professionals Regarding Their Profession

Data indicates that 23% doctors, 17% engineers, 22% Chartered accountants, 14% managers, 23% software engineers, 27% architects, 24% interior decorators, 21% dress designers, 13% teachers and 16% lawyers are impacted by career counseling and they took decision of career after guidance of career counselor. Hypothesis 1, there is a significant effect of career guidance and counseling on student's career development is accepted.

Table-2 shows that satisfaction level is higher for guided professionals rather than not guided by career counselors. Thus hypothesis 2 there is a significant effect of career guidance and counseling regarding job satisfaction is accepted. 86% engineers who are guided by counselors and 62% unguided engineers are satisfied. 91% doctors are satisfied who took guidance before entry in the field while without guidance doctor's satisfaction % is 73%. Chartered accountant's satisfaction % is 97% and 94% respectively. Same results obtained for all professionals indicating influence of career counselors.

6. Conclusion

In Indian educational frame work, career counseling is not a necessary step. Its influence on professional satisfaction shows its importance. Counseling includes many aspects of a person's life then provides options of career with priorities. If a student go along guided way he gets success and life satisfaction. Decision taken by without guidance may produce un satisfaction.

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